

Why Do Visitors Take Different Paths?

AI Insights into Social Interaction and Group Behaviour

Abstract

This paper analyses pedestrian movement and social interaction in Unity of Italy Square using computer vision based trajectory extraction and group identification. Although the plaza provides no predefined circulation routes, pedestrians do not move randomly. Instead, their paths reflect a combination of spatial affordances such as visibility and enclosure, as well as social coordination within walking groups. The study extracts movements from one week of video footage and categorises trajectories into individuals, pairs, and multi person groups. The findings indicate that individuals tend to explore a wider range of route possibilities, while socially interacting groups follow smoother and more homogeneous lines of movement. Although no formal syntactic calculations were conducted, the observed patterns align closely with principles from space syntax. Areas of high visibility support greater route diversity, whereas visually structured or perceptually anchored zones encourage convergence. This work provides empirical support for Social Wayfinding Theory and demonstrates the value of integrating AI based observations with spatial behaviour theory in open urban environments.

Keywords

Social Wayfinding; Computer vision; Social interaction; Pedestrian movement

1. Introduction

Urban squares are designed to provide openness, flexibility, and freedom of movement (Askarizad et al., 2025). Yet this very openness makes route choice ambiguous. Without kerbs, corridors, or predetermined pathways, pedestrians may walk directly across the centre, follow subtle visual lines, drift along the periphery, or walk together in socially coordinated patterns. Existing studies tend to model pedestrian movement as an individualised behaviour (Bae et al., 2024; Hillier et al., 1993; Moussaid et al., 2009; Wagnild and Wall-Scheffler, 2013), but in reality many people move through space while interacting—talking, waiting, adjusting speed, or coordinating direction with companions (Moussaid et al., 2009). These social processes are rarely captured in conventional mobility research. The concept of social wayfinding proposes that navigation is not only a spatial but also a social process: people observe and respond to the movements, intentions, and pace of those around them (Dalton et al., 2019). However, real data evidence supporting this idea has remained limited. This study attempts to bridge that gap by analysing a full week of crowd movement in a large open plaza, using video analytics-based trajectory extraction to examine how individuals and groups navigate differently under the same spatial context.

Urban squares are complex and multifunctional public spaces where pedestrian movement emerges from the interaction between spatial structure, visual information, and social behaviour (Askarizad et al., 2025). Unlike streets or corridors with clearly defined boundaries, open plazas offer few explicit cues for navigation. As a result, pedestrians must rely on a combination of spatial perception and interpersonal coordination to determine how to move across the space (Willis et al., 2004). Understanding such movement patterns is therefore essential for interpreting how people interact with the built environment.

Traditional studies of pedestrian navigation often conceptualise movement as an individual cognitive process shaped by distance, orientation, or environmental affordances (Hillier et al., 1993; Moussaid et al., 2009; Wagnild and Wall-Scheffler, 2013; Bae, Montello and Hegarty, 2024). In contrast, research on social behaviour highlights that many pedestrians walk not alone, but as part of socially organised units whose actions and decisions are interdependent (Moussaid et al., 2009). Social Wayfinding Theory

suggests that navigation frequently occurs within shared social contexts, where walking companions influence route choices, speed adjustments, and micro-scale decision-making (Dalton, Hölscher and Montello, 2019). This distinction is particularly relevant in open squares, where social groups must coordinate their movement without the assistance of explicit spatial channels.

Space syntax offers a complementary theoretical framework for analysing pedestrian movement by examining how the configuration of space influences visibility, integration, and the distribution of potential routes (Askarizad, 2024). This theory emphasises the profound influence of spatial structures on pedestrian behaviour, even in environments lacking physical pathways (Dong, 2025). Highly visible and spatially integrated areas tend to attract more movement, while visually fragmented or edge-defined regions can steer flows in more predictable ways (Hillier et al., 1993). Although spatial syntax has been widely applied in street networks, its implications for large, open squares—where paths are not predefined—remain understudied.

The integration of computer vision with spatial-behavioural theory offers a promising new direction (van Ameijde et al., 2025). Advances in detection and tracking models enable the extraction of detailed pedestrian trajectories at scale, allowing researchers to capture how individuals and groups actually move in real-world settings. Such data-driven approaches provide opportunities to test concepts from space syntax and social wayfinding using empirical evidence.

In this study, we analyse one week of pedestrian movement in Unity of Italy Square using an AI-based trajectory pipeline. The objective is to examine how individuals, pairs, and multi-person groups navigate the same spatial environment and to interpret their movement patterns through the dual lenses of social interaction and spatial configuration. By comparing trajectories with identical origin–destination conditions, the analysis reveals how differences in visibility structure and social organisation jointly influence route diversity. This work contributes empirical insight to an emerging intersection of spatial morphology, social interaction, and video analytics-based movement analysis.

2. Theory

Pedestrian movement has long been understood as a product of both spatial configuration and social behaviour. Space syntax theory provides one of the most influential frameworks for analysing how the built environment shapes movement patterns. Foundational work by Hillier (1993) argues that spatial layout influences how people navigate, even in the absence of explicit directional cues. Subsequent empirical studies confirm that areas with higher visibility and stronger spatial integration tend to attract greater pedestrian flows, while visually fragmented or edge-defined zones often channel movement into more stable and predictable lines (Batty, 2022).

These insights align with the concept of natural movement, which suggests that pedestrian flows emerge directly from the spatial configuration of the environment (Penn et al., 1998; Turner et al., 2001). In open squares, where no predetermined routes exist, visibility fields, spatial coherence, and the clarity of local vistas become especially important. High-visibility areas afford more choice and encourage exploratory movement, whereas visually structured axes help stabilise flow by reducing decision complexity.

Alongside spatial determinants, walking is also a deeply social activity. Social Wayfinding Theory proposes that people often navigate as part of small social units, coordinating pace, direction, and interpersonal distance (Dalton, Hölscher and Montello, 2019). Walking pairs tend to maintain side-by-side formations (Wagnild and Wall-Scheffler, 2013), and larger groups prioritise cohesion, which affects speed, path smoothness, and how they negotiate spatial obstacles (Moussaid et al., 2009). These behaviours indicate that navigation is shaped not only by spatial affordances but also by interpersonal dynamics.

Integrating spatial syntax with social pathfinding theory enables a more comprehensive understanding of pedestrian movement patterns: spatial structure determines “which paths are feasible”, while social relationships influence “how these paths are selected and traversed”.

3. Datasets and Methods

The study was conducted in the Unity of Italy Square, a fully open plaza with multiple entrances and no fixed walking corridors (Fig.1). The space attracts a mixture of tourists and locals, resulting in a rich diversity of movement patterns. The videos were sampled during three typical peak periods—morning (08:00–09:00), midday (12:00–13:00), and afternoon (17:00–18:00)—with each segment lasting 60 minutes. These videos provide a naturalistic dataset for understanding how pedestrians behave in an unstructured environment.

Fig. 1 Study site and data collection setup

To analyse pedestrian movement, a computer-vision-based pipeline was developed (Chen, Natapov and Ali, 2025). YOLOv7 was used to detect pedestrians in each frame, and DeepSORT assigned consistent tracking IDs to generate complete trajectories (Fig.2). After filtering noise and short-duration detections, each trajectory was mapped onto a calibrated coordinate system of the plaza. Origin and destination groups (OD group) were then defined so that trajectories sharing the same start and end points could be compared under equivalent conditions. Social interactions were identified through a rule-based method focusing on sustained proximity, synchronous movement, and behavioural consistency over at least ten seconds. Finally, Dynamic Time Warping and concentration index¹ were applied to quantify the diversity and similarity between any OD group trajectories, allowing an examination of how route diversity varies across individuals, pairs, and larger groups.

Fig. 2 Workflow of pedestrian trajectory extraction and origin-destination (OD) definition.

4. Result

The movement patterns observed in the square reveal a clear contrast between individual mobility and socially coordinated walking. When pedestrians travel alone, their trajectories unfold with remarkable freedom: even with identical origins and destinations, individuals disperse widely across the plaza, tracing

¹ To capture the extent of route convergence, we defined a concentration index:

$$C_i = \frac{\max_{k \in K_i}(n_{ik})}{N_i}$$

where K_i is the set of clusters for OD_i , n_{ik} is the size of cluster k , and $N_i = \sum_{k \in K_i} n_{ik}$ is the total number of trajectories. Higher values indicate stronger path convergence.

curved lines through the central open area, cutting diagonally across high-visibility zones, or drifting toward the edges before rejoining their intended direction. This expansive range of paths reflects an exploratory tendency shaped by the openness of the square and the absence of prescribed routes.

Once walking becomes a social activity, however, the fluidity of movement narrows. Pairs intuitively align their steps, adjusting pace and direction to remain coordinated, which results in smoother and more consistent trajectories across OD groups. These routes often cluster along visually continuous corridors, where maintaining side-by-side formation requires less negotiation. Larger groups show an even stronger convergence, favouring broad, legible passageways or peripheral movement lines that minimise internal disruption and preserve group cohesion. As illustrated in the clustered paths, individual trajectories fan outward, while multi-person groups compress into tight and unified bands.

Spatial patterns of stationary behaviour further support these observations (Fig. 3). Across morning, midday, and late-afternoon periods, dwell points consistently accumulate in highly visible edges and around major attractors such as the fountain and the open frontage toward the busiest entrance. Morning activity is sparse and dispersed, with individuals pausing at peripheral points; midday sees intensified gathering around central landmarks; and by late afternoon, dwell clusters expand into stable hotspots that align closely with lines of high intervisibility in the surrounding street network. These hotspots correspond to the same spatial affordances where paired and multi-person groups later produce the most concentrated movement paths.

Fig. 3 Temporal distribution of pedestrian activity across different time periods

Trajectory similarity assessments reinforce this spatial–social relationship (Fig. 4). Individuals exhibit the highest route diversity, pairs show intermediate convergence, and large groups display strongly overlapping trajectories within each OD cluster. These differences extend to movement speed: people walking alone tend to be the fastest, while multi-person groups move more slowly as they maintain spacing, visual contact, and collective alignment.

Fig. 4 Representative pedestrian trajectories by entrance and group type

Together, these findings show that navigating an open public space is shaped not only by spatial configuration but also by the social context of walking. What appears to be the same journey—from one

entrance to another—produces fundamentally different route patterns depending on whether a person walks alone, with a companion, or as part of a group, demonstrating how social dynamics and visibility structure jointly influence movement in public squares.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that pedestrian movement in an open public square is shaped by the combined influence of spatial visibility structures and social organisation. Even when starting and ending at the same points, individuals and social groups navigate the plaza in fundamentally different ways. Individuals disperse more widely and respond flexibly to local spatial affordances, while pairs and larger groups tend to converge towards smoother and more legible movement lines that support coordination and mutual monitoring. These patterns indicate that wayfinding is not solely an individual cognitive response to spatial configuration, but also a socially mediated process.

By integrating computer vision based trajectory extraction with spatial behavioural analysis, this research offers a transferable methodological framework for examining pedestrian movement in open and weakly structured public spaces. On this basis, the findings provide empirical support for Social Wayfinding Theory, showing that social context conditions route choice, movement variability, and walking speed, while also aligning closely with key principles of space syntax. Specifically, the results demonstrate that visibility, enclosure, and spatial continuity underpin the formation of dominant movement lines, particularly for social groups that depend on stable visual fields to maintain cohesion. In this sense, syntactic qualities of space become behaviourally meaningful through their interaction with social organisation.

Reference

- Askarizad, R., Lamíquiz Daudén, P. J., & Garau, C. (2024). The Application of Space Syntax to Enhance Sociability in Public Urban Spaces: A Systematic Review. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 13(7), 227. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi13070227>
- van Ameijde, J. et al. (2025) 'Decoding micro-social interactions in public space: a computer-vision-based method', *Computational Urban Science*, 5(1), p. 55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43762-025-00211-y>.
- Batty, M. (2022). Integrating space syntax with spatial interaction. *Urban Informatics*, 1(1), 4.
- Bae, C., Montello, D. and Hegarty, M. (2024) 'Wayfinding in pairs: comparing the planning and navigation performance of dyads and individuals in a real-world environment', *Cognitive Research: Principles and Implications*, 9(1), p. 40. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41235-024-00563-9>.
- Chen, W., Natapov, A. and Ali, Y. (2025) 'Can urban vitality be seen? Video analytics of social interaction and land use', *Land Use Policy*, 159, p. 107818. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2025.107818>.
- Dalton, R., Hölscher, C. and Montello, D.R. (2019) 'Wayfinding as a Social Activity', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, pp. 142–142. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00142>.
- Dong, W., Kang, Q., Wang, G., Hou, R., & Liu, P. (2025). Exploring the influence of path environment factors on walking behavior in urban parks with configuration attribute control. *Plos one*, 20(7), e0329278.
- Exploring the influence of path environment factors on walking behavior in urban parks with configuration attribute control* | *PLOS One* (no date). Available at: <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0329278> (Accessed: 15 November 2025).
- Hillier, B. et al. (1993) 'Natural Movement: Or, Configuration and Attraction in Urban Pedestrian Movement', *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 20(1), pp. 29–66. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1068/b200029>.
- Integrating space syntax with spatial interaction* | *Urban Informatics* (no date). Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s44212-022-00004-2> (Accessed: 15 November 2025).
- Moussaid, M. et al. (2009) 'Collective Information Processing and Pattern Formation in Swarms, Flocks, and Crowds', *Topics in Cognitive Science*, 1(3), pp. 469–497. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1756-8765.2009.01028.x>.
- Penn, A. et al. (1998) 'Configurational Modelling of Urban Movement Networks', *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 25(1), pp. 59–84. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1068/b250059>.
- Peponis, J., Zimring, C. and Choi, Y.K. (1990) 'Finding the Building in Wayfinding', *Environment and Behavior*, 22(5), pp. 555–590. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916590225001>.
- The Application of Space Syntax to Enhance Sociability in Public Urban Spaces: A Systematic Review* (no date). Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2220-9964/13/7/227> (Accessed: 2 November 2025).
- Turner, A. et al. (2001) 'From Isovists to Visibility Graphs: A Methodology for the Analysis of Architectural Space', *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 28(1), pp. 103–121. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1068/b2684>.
- Wagnild, J. and Wall-Scheffler, C.M. (2013) 'Energetic Consequences of Human Sociality: Walking Speed Choices among Friendly Dyads', *PLoS ONE*, 8(10), p. e76576. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0076576>.

Willis, A. *et al.* (2004) 'Human Movement Behaviour in Urban Spaces: Implications for the Design and Modelling of Effective Pedestrian Environments', *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 31(6), pp. 805–828. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1068/b3060>.